

Multifunctional Carbon Nanotube-based Composite Carbon Fibers for Enhanced Mechanical Properties

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we demonstrate an alternative strategy for enhancing the mechanical performance of carbon fibers by incorporating polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) into carbon nanotube (CNT)-based systems via a CSA-assisted wet-spinning approach. PPS, typically insoluble and highly crystalline, was successfully processed to form composite fibers, which exhibited significant improvements in tensile properties following thermal treatment. The results indicate the effectiveness of PPS incorporation without traditional stabilization steps. This method may provide a scalable and cost-effective route for multifunctional carbon fiber production.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotube (CNT) fibers have gained recognition as a potential next-generation carbon fiber due to their outstanding mechanical and electrical properties [1-6]. Efforts to enhance CNT fiber performance have primarily focused on increasing CNT length or crystallinity, but these strategies face thermodynamic and practical limitations [7-8]. As an alternative, researchers have begun incorporating other carbon materials or polymers into CNT fibers to leverage synergistic effects and reduce reliance on costly CNTs [9-11].

Wet-spinning of CNT fibers using chlorosulfonic acid (CSA) offers a versatile platform, as CSA can not only dissolve CNTs but also sulfonate otherwise insoluble polymers [10-16]. This enables the co-processing of CNTs with sulfonated polymers into composite fibers. These sulfonated polymers are advantageous in that they can generate radicals during pyrolysis, which in turn form covalent bonds with CNTs—either between CNTs themselves or between CNTs and polymer chains [17-20]. This radical-mediated crosslinking enhances the structural cohesion and mechanical integrity of the resulting carbon fibers [21-24].

Carbon nanotube (CNT) fibers have attracted considerable attention as a new class of carbon fiber materials due to their exceptional electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties. However, their broad commercialization remains constrained by high production costs and technical limitations related to CNT alignment and interfacial bonding. Recent approaches have explored hybridization with polymers to enhance spinnability, reduce cost, and improve mechanical integrity.

Among these, poly(p-phenylene sulfide) (PPS) presents a promising option due to its aromatic backbone and high carbon yield upon pyrolysis. Despite its poor solubility in most solvents, PPS can be sulfonated and processed in chlorosulfonic acid (CSA), forming anisotropic liquid crystalline dopes in combination with CNTs [25-30]. This co-processing enables the fabrication of CNT-PPS composite fibers via wet-spinning. Upon carbonization, the composite fibers benefit from radical-mediated crosslinking between PPS and CNTs, potentially improving the mechanical integrity of the final carbon fiber.

In this study, we examine the structural and mechanical evolution of CNT-PPS fibers as a function of PPS content and heat-treatment temperature. Our goal is to establish processing-structure-property relationships that support the design of high-performance CNT-based carbon fibers using PPS as a functional additive and carbon source.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The wet-spinning process allowed for uniform mixing of CNTs and sulfonated PPS (sPPS), forming composite fibers with smooth morphology and good spinnability even at high PPS loadings. Following drying and heat treatment, structural transformations such as de-sulfonation and crosslinking led to noticeable changes in fiber morphology and density.

Thermal analysis revealed that sPPS enhanced the thermal stability and char yield of the composite fibers. This was attributed to the generation of radicals during thermal decomposition, which promoted covalent bonding within the fiber structure. These interactions supported better structural coherence and higher carbon retention.

Mechanical testing showed that the incorporation of PPS improved tensile strength and modulus after carbonization. An optimal PPS content of around 30 wt% yielded the best performance, balancing reinforcement from PPS-derived carbon with effective load transfer through CNT-PPS bonding. Excessive PPS content, however, led to turbostratic structures and reduced mechanical integrity due to misalignment and void formation.

Small-angle and wide-angle X-ray scattering analyses confirmed that increasing PPS disrupted CNT alignment, which impacted the modulus. Transmission electron microscopy further visualized turbostratic carbon domains originating from sPPS, which were distinguishable from CNT regions.

Overall, the combination of PPS and CNTs, processed through CSA-assisted wet-spinning and tailored heat treatment, enabled the production of carbon fibers with improved mechanical properties and structural integrity. The findings highlight the importance of optimizing composite composition and processing conditions to maximize performance.

3 FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: (a) The possible structure of sPPS using CSA, (b) XPS of sPPS, (c) GC-MS of sPPS and possible molecules corresponding to each peak of MS. Reprinted from *Carbon* 219 (2024) 118814

Figure 2: Proposed mechanisms of interaction between radical from sPPS and CNT. Reprinted from *Carbon* 219 (2024) 118814

Figure 3: (a) Stress-strain curves (b) Specific tensile strength, (c) Specific tensile modulus and (d) Toughness of CNT-PPS composite fibers and their heat-treated fibers, (e) Specific tensile strength of CP73 and CP37 depending on heat-treatment temperature, (f) Comparison of CNT-PPS fibers with other CNTFs [30-34] and commercial CFs. Reprinted from *Carbon* 219 (2024) 118814

Figure 4: (a) 2D SAXS patterns, (b) Misalignment, (c) Length, (d) Thickness and (e) Volume of 1400 °C-carbonized CNT–PPS composite fibers, (f) Schematic diagram of enlargement of voids in the fibers after carbonization, (g) WAXS pattern images of 1400 °C-carbonized CNT–PPS composite fibers, (h) CNT orientation factor along the fiber axis. Reprinted from *Carbon* 219 (2024) 118814

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated a practical route for manufacturing CNT-based composite carbon fibers by incorporating sulfonated PPS through a liquid crystalline wet-spinning process. The fibers exhibited improved mechanical properties after controlled thermal treatment, attributed to enhanced carbon yield and covalent interaction between CNTs and PPS. The optimized composites balanced CNT alignment with polymer-derived carbon reinforcement, resulting in high-performance structural materials. This approach holds promise for scalable and cost-effective production of next-generation carbon fibers

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